

BENEFITS OF USING KAHOOT DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL PLATFORM IN TEACHING ENGLISH

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7940935>

Khalilova Olima Akhatovna

The senior teacher of Foreign Language department, Karshi Engineering Economic Institute

olimaahatovna67@gmail.com

Abstract.

At the present stage, one of the main tasks of modern teachers of foreign languages is to improve the quality of education and upbringing, excellent knowledge of the subject. Educational reforms and updating of educational programs require the development of models of the educational process of a new type, the creation of new teaching aids using the latest technologies, curricula and the development of new teaching methods. The article reveals some of the problems of using digital educational platforms and the benefits of using the Kahoot application in organizing and conducting interesting and effective English lessons.

Keywords.

information and communication technologies, online learning, platform, internal motivation, effective lessons.

Introduction.

Today, the use of information and communication technologies in teaching English is one of the most important aspects of improving the educational process. These technologies contribute to the development of intellectual and creative abilities of students increase the motivation of students. Information and communication technologies make it possible to increase the effectiveness of training, the intellectual level of students, to diversify the forms of interpersonal communication of all participants in the educational process, to improve the methods of conducting classes, thus opening up new opportunities in teaching[5,130].

The online applications help students solve complex problems, improve communication and leadership skills, increase productivity, creativity, create presentations, distinguish between reliable and unreliable online sources, maintain proper online etiquette, and write emails. The use of these technologies helps

teachers to fill the lessons with new content, creates a favorable atmosphere for working in the classroom, accelerates the learning process and increases students' interest in the subject. The appropriate use of ICT technology makes the English lesson more entertaining and effective.

Main part:

The Kahoot online educational platform allows teachers to easily and quickly create various educational games, quizzes, tests without leaving their home, university or office.

The first thing a teacher needs to do is create an account on getkahoot.com. Go to sign up to create an account. Select As a teacher. When you already have an account, we select Create new to start creating the game. For each topic, we can ask as many questions as we want. Each question has four possible answers, including one correct one [35,352]. The correct option will be selected by the teacher, and a tick will be placed to the right of which. The teacher can choose the appropriate duration for each question depending on the difficulty of the question. In addition, we can also insert relevant images or videos into the question to grab students' attention and interest. The type of exercise to choose the right one from the given options is very suitable for teaching listening, reading or grammar. After composing the first question, we click Add question to move on to the next question.

The teacher can organize the game so that all students play together in the class at the same time. This game can also be effective in online learning, with each group of students sitting at home. To take part in the game, students log into kahoot.it from their smartphone, tablet or laptop, enter the pin code provided by the teacher, and then give the player a name. Each player's name will appear in the teacher's Kahoot interface, so the teacher can rate each student's ability by the number of correct answers they get. The winning student will receive the highest score.

Pros Kahoot App:

- The app is simple and easy to use;
- Exercises done in a playful way arouse students' interest;
- The teacher can evaluate the learning of the lesson by the points scored by the students in the game.

Cons of the Kahoot app: - In class, when users play games through the Kahoot app, an internet connection is required. Students must connect to the game at the same time.

Students can answer tests created by the teacher from tablets, laptops, smartphones, that is, from any device with Internet access.

Assignments created in Kahoot allow teachers to include photos and even video clips. The pace of quizzes and tests is regulated by the introduction of a time limit for each question. If desired, the teacher can enter points for answering questions: for correct answers and for speed. The scoreboard is displayed on the teacher's computer monitor. To participate in testing, students just need to open the service and enter the PIN code provided by the teacher from their computer. It is convenient for the student to choose the correct answer on their device [45,261]. Options are represented by geometric shapes. Using this service can be a good way to get original feedback from students. One of the features of Kahoot is the ability to duplicate and edit tests, which saves the teacher a lot of time. In addition to quizzes with Kahoot, teachers can start a discussion by starting a discussion with a single question, or conduct a multi-question poll and then start a debate.

The use of the Kahoot application in English lessons greatly contributes to the development of internal motivation of students, they like to learn new things, they become interested in learning a foreign language and conditions are created for achieving certain success.

The advantage of this application is that users can compose multiple choice questions in a playful way - a very interesting type of assignment that encourages students to use information technology and healthy competition. With an attractive design and features, Kahoot will help students compete fairly for the ability to

answer questions as quickly as possible. Moreover, this type of exercise helps students learn while playing, increasing their interest.

Conclusion:

The use of information and communication technologies in teaching allows all users to acquire independently knowledge, and reduces the need for intermediary activities of a teacher, since independent work with electronic learning tools is the basis of the educational process. Modern network technologies provide access to a huge amount of educational, methodological and scientific literature; help to conduct virtual classes in real time [14,11]. Information and communication technologies include a variety of methods and software and hardware tools for working with data. These include electronic textbooks and manuals, electronic encyclopedias and reference books, gaming platforms and testing programs, a wide range of educational resources on the Internet.

Thus, the Kahoot application helps to increase students' motivation and interest in the language being studied, greatly facilitates the learning process for the teacher, and brings joy to the students from the learning process.

REFERENCES:

1. AMINOVA ZP, KHALILOVA OA. MATERIALS IN ESP COURSES. Иностранные языки в Узбекистане. 2019(3):83-93. <https://journal.fledu.uz/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2019/08/article-5604-1507.pdf>.
2. Badalova, L. (2022). Development of the cognitive interest of students in teaching a foreign language at a technical university. Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes, 174-176. <http://conferenceseries.info/index.php/online/article/view/79>.
3. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna. (2022). Formation of Intercultural Competence in Teaching the Translation of Economic Texts. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 6, 14-19. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejlat/article/view/801>.
4. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS // ORIENSS. 2021. №5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/innovative-methods-of-teaching-in-educational-institution>.

5. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna. (2022). NEW TRENDS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE. Open Access Repository, 8(03), 130-133. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/RK8HX>.
6. Erkinovna , Y. F. . (2023). Grice's Conversational Maxims in Our Everyday Life. Miasto Przyszłości, 32, 151-154. <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1118>.
7. Khalilova OA. Teaching speaking: examples of oral communicative activities. Міжнародний науковий журнал Інтернаука. 2017(2 (2)):32-4. <https://www.inter-nauka.com/uploads/public/1490953057675.pdf#page=33>.
8. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. (2023). STYLISTICS AND STYLE: A HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE AND RECENT TRENDS. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 11(4), 607-610. Retrieved from <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/3858>.
9. Khalilova O.A. FUNDAMENTALS OF LEXICOLOGY // Экономика и социум. 2021. №3-1 (82). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/fundamentals-of-lexicology> (дата обращения: 12.04.2023).
10. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. (2022). Teaching Pronunciation Skills. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 5, 279-282. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjm/article/view/888>.
11. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna, Obzorov Islom Ruzievich. Prospects of the energy system in Uzbekistan. Int J Appl Res 2020;6(5):306-307. <https://www.allresearchjournal.com/archives/?year=2020&vol=6&issue=5&part=E&ArticleId=6717>.
12. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. (2023). CLT PLAY AN IMPORTANT ROLE TO LEARN LANGUAGE EFFECTIVELY. World Bulletin of Management and Law, 21, 133-136. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbml/article/view/2571>.
13. Khalilova OA. Organizational Aspects of Developing Innovative Methods in Teaching. Eastern European Scientific Journal. 2018 Apr 10(2). <http://journale.auris-verlag.de/index.php/EESJ/article/viewFile/891/965>.
14. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. TECHNOLOGY IN LANGUAGE TEACHLNG. ajps [Internet]. 2022 Nov. 8 [cited 2023 Apr. 24];2(11):11-6. Available from: <https://theusajournals.com/index.php/ajps/article/view/460>.
15. Khujanovich, E. U. (2023). The Effectiveness of using Mobile Applications in Teaching a Foreign Language. Miasto Przyszłości, 32, 288-292. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1150>.

16. Kurbanov, S. (2022). МЕСТО КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ МЕТОДАХ ОБУЩЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 18(18). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/7427.
17. Madaminovich, T. I., Khusanovich, K. B., Akhatovna, K. O., & Kholmamatovna, B. L. (2019). Features of the System of Formation of Compensatory Competence Among Agricultural Students as a Means of Filling in Professional Terminology. In International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (Vol. 8, Issue 11, pp. 2202-2206). Blue Eyes Intelligence Engineering and Sciences Engineering and Sciences Publication - BEIESP. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijitee.k2039.0981119>.
18. Mansurova Gulbahor Makhdievna. (2022). Teaching the Interpretation of a Literary Text in German Lessons. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 6, 27-31. Retrieved from <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejlat/article/view/803>.
19. Mansurova, G. M., & Fayzieva, K. A. (2020). GENERAL CRITERIA FOR THE EVALUATION CATEGORY. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 2(8), 227-230. https://scholar.google.ru/scholar?hl=ru&as_sdt=0,5&cluster=1242523419625242789.
20. Mansurova, Gulbahor and Fayzieva, Kamila (2019) "EVALUATION CATEGORY IN FOREIGN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES ACCORDING TO THEIR PRAGMATIC CHARACTERISTICS." Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University: Vol. 1: Iss. 2, Article 41. Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/namdu/vol1/iss2/41>
21. Mansurova GM, Eshonkulova NT, Eshmurodov UK. THE TRAGEDY OF "JULIUS CAESAR". Социосфера. 2021(1):54-6. http://www.sociosfera.com/files/conference/2021/sociosfera_1-21.pdf#page=55.
22. Mirkhaydarovna, J. S., Irkinovna, D. N., Abdimuminovna, C. S., Shamsievna, I. P., & Kholmamatovna, B. L. (2023). Intensive Methods of Improving Linguistic Competence in the Russian Language of Students of Non-Linguistic Higher Education Institutions in Uzbekistan. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*, 10(2S), 3518-3528. [Intensive Methods of Improving Linguistic Competence in the Russian Language of Students of Non-Linguistic Higher Education Institutions in Uzbekistan | Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences \(sifisheriessciences.com\)](https://www.sifisheriessciences.com).

23. Nazarova, N. (2022). Обучение молодых учащихся через интерактивные игры. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 7(7).
извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/49.
24. Nazarova, N. (2022). ЛЕКСИКО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ АНТРОПОНИМОВ . ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 25(25).
извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/8279.
25. Nazarova, N. (2022). Лингвистическое исследование антропонимов в лексической системе. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 13(13).
извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/6674.
26. Niyazova Yulduz Tashmuradovna. (2023). GAMIFICATION IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY. International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. FARS Publishers, 11(2), 912–917. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689661>.
27. Niyazova Yu. T. Comprehend simple grammatical errors and effective ways of teaching grammar / Yu. T. Niyazova // Міжнародний науковий журнал "Інтернаука" . - 2017. - № 5. - С. 43-44. - Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/mnj_2017_5_12.
28. Niyazova, Y. (2022). BASIC PRINCIPLES OF LISTENING TECHNOLOGY. *Scientific Collection «InterConf»*, (110), 93–98. Retrieved from <https://archive.interconf.center/index.php/conference-proceeding/article/view/455>.
29. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna Main components of organizing independent work of students // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №4 (17). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/main-components-of-organizing-independent-work-of-students>(дата обращения: 30.03.2023).
30. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna Some features of effective teaching professionally oriented foreign language // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №4 (17). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/some-features-of-effective-teaching-professionally-oriented-foreign-language>(дата обращения: 30.03.2023).
31. Solieva Munavvar Ahmadovna 2022. Appeal in the Structure of Speech Etiquette. International Journal on Integrated Education. 5, 6 (Jun. 2022), 158-161. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v5i6.3143>.

32. Tashmuradovna , N. Y. . (2023). The Function of Phrasal Verbs as Lexical Material in Business English. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 32, 272–276. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1146>.

33. Umedilloevna, S. M. UDC: 1751 Lexicographic Analysis Of The Concise Oxford Dictionary Of Literary Terms By K. Boldik And Some Uzbek Literary Dictionaries. *Scientific Reports Of Bukhara State University*, 115. https://buxdu.uz/media/jurnallar/ilmiy_axborot/ilmiy_axborot_5_son_2020.pdf#page=117.

34. O. L. Liu, B. Bridgeman, R. M. Adler Measuring learning outcomes in higher education: Motivation matters *Educational Researcher*, 41 (9) (2012), pp. 352–362

35. Саидова, М. (2021). THE CONCISE OXFORD DICTIONARY OF LITERARY TERMS. ЛУЕАТИДАГИ ДРАМА АДАБИЙ ТУРИГА ХОС ТЕРМИНЛАРИНИНГ МАЗМУНИЙ ТАДЛИЛИ//ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. Uz), (8). https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/445

36. Saidova, M. U. (2020). LEXICOGRAPHIC AND ETHYMOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCISE OXFORD DICTIONARY OF LITERARY TERMS BY. <https://namdu.researchcommons.org/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?Article=2723&context=journal>.

37. Saidova, M. U. The problem of studying literary terms on figurative language. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=ru&as_sdt=0,5&cluster=9219256601546054307.

38. Usmonova, Z. H. (2021). The peculiarity of fantastic works (on the example of the works of Ray Bradbury, Isaac Asimov and Stephen King). *European Scholar Journal*, 2(4), 499-503. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/394826-none-ac04ea4d.pdf>

39. Yuldasheva, f. (2023). Исследования вежливости в современной лингвистике. центр научных публикаций (buxdu.Uz), 31(31). https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/9211.

40. Yuldasheva, f. (2023). Выражение вежливости в речевом этикете. центр научных публикаций (buxdu.Uz), 31(31). https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/9214.

41. Yuldasheva Feruza Erkinovna. (2022). The Principle of Politeness in the English and Uzbek Languages. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 6, 65–70. Retrieved from <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb/article/view/799>.

42. Zarina Habibovna Usmonova. (2021). THE PECULIARITY OF FANTASTIC WORKS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE WORKS OF RAY BRADBURY, ISAAC ASIMOV AND STEPHEN KING). *European Scholar Journal*, 2(4), 499-503. Retrieved from <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/esj/article/view/684>.

43. Саидова, Мухайё. "Inglizcha poetik terminlarning o'zbek tilida berilishida shakl va mazmun munosabati." ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz) 13.13. (2022). https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/6714.

44. Umidullayevna, Saidova Mukhayyo. "SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH POETIC TERMS IN LITERARY DICTIONARIES." RESEARCH AND EDUCATION 1.1 (2022): 38- <https://researchedu.org/index.php/re/article/view/682>.

45. Солиева, М. (2021). ASSESSING THE KNOWLEDGE OF STUDENTS ON THE MOODLE PLATFORM. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 1(1). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/2547.

46. Солиева, М. (2022). РЕЧЕВЫЕ ПРАВИЛА ЭТИКИ КАК ОБЪЕКТ ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОГО ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 8(8). https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4858.

47. Шаяхметов, Ш. Г. Использование образовательной аналитики Kahoot для индивидуализации обучения / Ш. Г. Шаяхметов. – Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. – 2021. – № 45 (387). – С. 261-263. – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/387/85116/> (дата обращения: 05.05.2023).

48. Цифровые образовательные ресурсы в школе: методика использования. Начальная школа: сборник учебно-методических материалов для педагогических вузов. Отв. ред. Н. П. Безрукова. Москва: Университетская книга, 2008.